

Reproducibility of Expert Finding in Legal Community Question Answering

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Abstract. Expert finding is a challenging problem in the legal domain, where the knowledge gap is big between inexperienced citizens and expert lawyers. In the work "Expert Finding in the Legal Community Question Answering", Askari, Verberne, and Pasi propose a legal expert finding system by combining existing probabilistic and BERT-based ranking models with constructed query-based lawyer profiles. In this paper, we summarize and question the proposed methodologies and the final results of their work. We outline the challenges in the reproducibility of their experiments posed by incomplete specifications in both their publicized paper [1] and provided source code repository [2].

CCS Concepts: • **Information systems** → **Expert search**; **Question answering**; • **General and reference** → *Experimentation*; *Design*.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Legal Expert Finding, Experiment Design, Reproducibility

1 Introduction

Expert finding can be defined as the challenge of assessing and finding the required know-how for a certain assignment, that is, finding the right person for the right task. This interdisciplinary problem of information retrieval and knowledge management becomes more difficult when the skill gap is large between searchers and experts. In the legal domain, this holds true for the regular citizen seeking suitable advice from a professional lawyer on a community question answering (CQA) platform. As such, facilitating and automatizing the process of finding the best lawyers for a legal issue is an attractive proposal for both the uninformed clients and job-seeking attorneys.

In the article "Expert Finding in the Legal Community Question Answering", Askari, Verberne, and Pasi propose topic-based models and expert profiling methods to solve the problem of finding knowledgeable lawyers given a certain legal field. In this paper, we quickly outline the methodology of their work and extend the provided explanations necessary to understand the proposed experimental process. We discuss the challenges and feasibility of reproducing the presented results based on their paper [1] and provided source code [2], and scrutinize the conclusions drawn.

2 Theoretical Approach

Askari, Verberne, and Pasi tackle the legal expert finding problem in CQA systems by generating query-dependent textual profiles for professional lawyers based on their activity in a judicial online forum. The activity of each lawyer is assessed by their answers to legal questions, and profiles are generated by assessing the *recency*, *sentiment*, and *comments* of each answer. The resulting profiles combined with existing expert finding methods are then supposed to quantify the level of knowledge of an attorney [1]. That is, given a *query* term for a legal topic, the retrieval task of the constructed models is to successfully return a ranked list of lawyers who likely have high expertise in the field.

The topic-based baselines proposed for realizing the mapping of legal queries to suitable lawyers are characterized as either *candidate-based* models or *document-based* models. The former models assess the knowledge of a lawyer (candidate) for each query by evaluating all the answers written by them. The latter models revolve around aggregating the relevance scores of each answer

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(document) across multiple queries. Using either principle, a *probabilistic language model* calculates the likelihood $p(ca|q)$ of a candidate ca being an expert for a query topic q and ranks the lawyers accordingly [3]. A document-based *neural ranking model* instead estimates the relevance of different answers for a query and subsequently orders the authoring lawyers [6]. The final performance of each model can be used as a baseline assessment of whether the inclusion of the generated lawyer profiles provides a statistically significant improvement for the expert finding methods or not.

3 Experimental Setup

The proposed expert finding approach is studied on a web-scraped data set of questions and answers found in the juridical QCA forum Avvo [5]. The questions in the forum are written by anonymous users and the answers are given by professional lawyers; one may think of the web pages Avvo and better-known Stack Overflow as services offering analogous functionality for the legal and programming domain. Each question asked in Avvo is annotated with different *category tags*, asked for a certain location of city and state in the US, and posted on a certain date. These category tags are provided as *queries* to the topic-based models for the construction of the ranked list of lawyers. The quality of a given answer is indicated by the count of *helpful* and *lawyers agree* ratings, which are akin to the number of up-votes by regular citizens and professional lawyers, respectively. For each question, the person asking may accept a certain answer as the *best* answer, whereas the answer with the highest number of helpful votes is labeled as the *most helpful* [4].

The figure shows a screenshot of a legal question and its answers on the Avvo forum. The question is titled "Question Title" and is described as "Question description by anonymous citizen." It has tags for "Bankruptcy", "Tag 2", and "Tag 3", and a "Show 1 more" link. It was asked in City Q, CA on July 01, 2016, and has 2 answers. Below the question are two answers. The first answer is by "Lawyer X", a "Bankruptcy Attorney in City X, CA", posted on July 01, 2016, and is "Voted as Most Helpful". It has 2 helpful votes, 1 comment, and 3 lawyers agree. The second answer is by "Lawyer Y", a "Bankruptcy Attorney in City Y, CA", posted on July 02, 2016, and is "Selected as best answer". It has 1 helpful vote, 1 comment, and 4 lawyers agree.

Fig. 1. Example of a legal question and its answers on the Avvo forum [5].

The ground truth labels of whether a lawyer is defined as an expert for a query category are based on the criteria of (1) *engagement*, (2) *quality*, and (3) *quality ratio* of their given answers. The engagement of a lawyer is sufficient when (1) at least ten of their answers are accepted as best answers by the asking users. The lawyer gives enough qualitative answers when (2) an above-average number of their answers are marked as best answers or have more than three lawyers agree. The quality ratio of a lawyer's answers is high when (3) the proportion of their qualitative answers to overall answers is greater than the average [1]. The threshold chosen in condition (1) is

equal to one standard deviation above the average number of best answers over all lawyers and categories [10]. Naturally, the questions, answers, and averages considered pertain to only the current category for which the experts are to be determined. Notice that the given votes for helpful and most helpful answers are disregarded for the definition of labels. That is, the ratings of other attorneys and the user asking the question are considered central for establishing the notion of expertise, but the opinions of regular citizens are not.

The web-scraped data set is restricted to questions given the category tag “bankruptcy”, although each question may be annotated by multiple other tags. Moreover, both the user asking and the lawyer responding must reside in the same city in the state of California and the questions and answers must have been posted between the period of July 2016 to July 2021. The obtained list of questions is used to count the number of occurrences of all the different category tags co-occurring with “bankruptcy” and construct a list of candidate lawyers providing answers. For the top 20 percent of common category tags, the corresponding lawyer labels are derived based on the expert criteria defined above. The category tags of the subset with at least two experts are employed as the final queries for the expert finding models. The constructed data is split into three-thirds of train, validation, and test sets disjoint on the experts to avoid over-fitting on already seen lawyers [1].

The first baseline models evaluating the queries are two probabilistic language models denoted as *LM* and *BM25* implementing both the candidate-based and document-based ranking approach [1]. A document-based neural ranking model denoted as *Vanilla BERT* serves as the second baseline [6]. The tested expert model proposed by Askari, Verberne, and Pasi constructs query-dependent lawyer profiles and uses a weighted combination with the BERT-based model to derive the predicted expert list for each query. A more extensive explanation of the legal expert finding models constructed can be found in the original paper [1].

4 Reproducibility

The GitHub repository provided [2] contains relevant data files for the questions considered, the number of occurrences of all involved category tags, the resulting final queries, and the corresponding experts used in the outlined expert finding experiment. The proposed topic-based models are also partially implemented as Python scripts in the source code. Both the candidate-based and document-based LM model can be found in the same repository [2], the document-based Vanilla BERT model is reused from an external project [7], and the BM25 model is missing completely.

The data set questions are listed purely as hyperlinks to the legal forum Avvo and thus their content needs to be fetched from the website. We web-scrape the questions and corresponding answers using the open-source web application library *Selenium* [8] in Python by simulating a web user that visits each question link. The simulated user opens the link in his browser, accepts the required cookies, and triggers various “show more” actions necessary to display the complete information of the question. The concrete data retrieved is based on the information needed for the assessment of the expert criteria and the construction of the models as outlined in Section 3.

Table 1. Comparison of collected bankruptcy data.

# Total data	Original	Replicate	# Expert data	Original	Replicate
Questions	9 897	3 288	C(1) threshold	10	2
Answers	93 565	11 708	Answers	5 614	4 361
Lawyers	3 741	2 016	Quality answers	1 917	1 580
Experts	61	57	Queries	84	45
Queries	844	658			

We pre-process and subsequently persist the obtained CQA data in a relational database structure. The relational database facilitates the assessment of relevant category tags as the final queries and their corresponding expert lawyers.

Table 2. Comparison of five most common category tags.

# Tag occurrences	Original	Replicate
Debt	9893	3286
Bankruptcy and debt	9892	3286
Bankruptcy	9892	3286
Credit	2959	852
Chapter 7 bankruptcy	2089	576

We split the final queries and answers into three-thirds of train, validation, and test sets based on the corresponding expert lawyers. We adapt the data splits to abide by the format required in the Python scripts of the candidate-based and document-based LM model and consequently reuse the implementations of the native source code repository [2]. Given that the source code for the BM25 model is not present, we follow the standardized definition [9] of the probabilistic model and recreate its presumable implementation. The employment of the document-based Vanilla BERT model is similarly not straightforward as the implementation is provided by an older paper [6] and external repository [7], and requires modifications to fit the current experiment. The definitions and granularity of experts and their answers of the external work seemingly conflict with the original paper [1], and we ultimately fail in adopting the implementation of the BERT model. Finally, we measure the performance of predicting the correct experts of a query for each reproduced model, using the evaluation metrics of MAP, MRR, and precision of predicting k lawyers.

Table 3. Performance results of reproducible baseline models.

Baseline model	MAP	MRR	P@1	P@2	P@5
Candidate-based LM	0.0906	0.1676	0.0417	0.0625	0.0667
Document-based LM	0.0291	0.0609	0	0.0114	0.0227
Candidate-based BM25	0.0388	0.0478	0	0	0.0417
Document-based BM25	0.0319	0.0379	0	0	0.0273

Whereas Askari, Verberne, and Pasi investigate statistically significant differences between each of the topic-based models, we are now also interested in determining if there is a significant discrepancy between the performances of the initial and reproduced models. In the original paper, the authors employ a *one-tailed t-test* with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ to measure whether the generated lawyer profiles provide a statistically significant improvement over the baselines. Here, we make use of a *paired t-test* and a *Wilcoxon signed-rank test* to compare the original and recreated performance results of MAP, MRR, and Precision@k between each equivalently implemented model. We express the magnitude of difference between each model performance using the standardized effect size of *Cohen’s d*. The analysis also includes an *ANOVA test* to evaluate if the reproduced results obtained significantly differ as a whole. At the $\alpha = 0.05$ level, the paired t-test shows a statistically significant difference for most of the models, whereas the Wilcoxon signed-rank test does not. The only exception is the candidate-based BM25 model, given that the predictions of that

baseline model were already very inaccurate in the original paper. Given the small sample size of paired performances, it is difficult to judge whether the normality assumption of the t-test is valid or not. The values of Cohen’s d effect size suggest that the differences in the reproduced model performances are very large, making the paired t-test more believable. The ANOVA test likewise suggests an overall statistically significant difference across the combined groups of performance results. That is, the statistical analysis shows there is most likely a meaningful difference between the recreated performance metrics and the original results of the paper. The final source code is available for replication and future work.¹

Table 4. Statistical comparison between reproduced and original model performance.

Baseline model	Paired t-test p	Wilcoxon p	Cohen’s d
Candidate-based LM	0.0067	0.0625	-1.9288
Document-based LM	0.0031	0.0625	-2.9289
Candidate-based BM25	0.3061	0.4375	-0.4254
Document-based BM25	0.0068	0.0625	-3.0231
ANOVA: F-statistic = 22.944, p-value = 0.00003			

5 Conclusion

Without even addressing the conclusions of the work of Askari, Verberne, and Pasi [1], one may notice that the presented intermediate results already greatly differ. This evident discrepancy can be attributed to various reasons, mostly stemming from unclear and missing specifications for both the experimental process and source code repository of the paper.

Firstly, the important definition of expert criteria described in the original work stands in contradiction to the principles of answer ratings in Avvo [4] due to inconsistent references to the forum elements. As outlined in Section 3, the vocabulary of the legal forum includes the terms “best” and “most helpful” when rating the answers of an attorney. The authors instead make vague references to “most useful” and “accepted” answers and also redefine the meaning of “best” answers, leaving ambiguity in their original intentions.

Secondly, the test data of the actual questions used is not archived in a static database and instead is only provided as temporal hyperlinks. It is common knowledge that the content of any web source is bound to change and the question links of the Avvo forum are no exception. Even if certain legal questions in the data list have received new lawyer answers over the past years, the presumptive original state of each question could be restored by filtering on the posted date. However, lawyers can also change or delete their answers in the forum and the inquiring citizen might even delete the complete question, leading to irretrievable missing data.

Furthermore, important general elements of the provided GitHub repository [2] are incomplete and the omitted information is not justifiable by the associated explanations in the original paper. For instance, there is neither instruction nor any code given on how the legal data set required was fetched from the CQA forum Avvo. Furthermore, the labeling of lawyers can be deemed ambiguous because of the reasons stated above, and no runnable code is given that reproduces the ground truth of experts. Although the repository includes a relational file that contains the resulting mapping between queries and expert lawyers, the list is incomplete based on the number of unique experts stated in the paper. The constructed train, validation, and test split of the data is also hardly reproducible, given that the procedure of the splitting is again missing a detailed description.

¹<https://github.com/theo-dorfner/ExDD-legal-CQA>

Lastly and most critically, some of the topic-based models have both no clear definition and no programmatic implementation but are consulted for the principal evaluation of the paper results. The settings and the implementation of the candidate-based and document-based BM25 model are missing completely. Although a conventional BM25 model can be easily programmed, the result is nothing but a presumable re-implementation based on empty assumptions. The document-based Vanilla BERT model implemented in the extern repository [7] needs to be manually adjusted for the actual project. No instructions are given on how to translate the concepts of lawyers and answers over to the cited work and the performed fine-tuning and utilized hyperparameters in the actual paper are not known either. Even if one would manage to convert the external source code to a runnable state or create a custom BERT-based implementation, using the resulting model seems impractical without any guidance. Even more so, the generation of the query-based textual lawyer profiles seems sufficiently explained by the authors but again completely lacks any source code implementation. Given that the profile ranking model is presented as the central result of the paper and proposed as a solution to legal expert finding, any divergence from the original implementation should be undesirable. However, most of the outlined reproducibility issues make it seemingly impossible to derive the same methods and implementation as the original authors. Given the lack of static data and missing model implementations, the consultation of statistical significance tests also becomes unreliable. The paired performance metrics between the original and reproduced model represent the same evaluation on hardly equivalent models using hardly equivalent training and test data. As such, any measured statistically significant differences are ambiguous, as they could truly be caused by disputable methods in the original paper, or just stem from the differently conducted experiment. That is, the actual results of the discussed scientific paper can neither be verified nor challenged if they cannot be fully reproduced.

Overall, the issues of lacking transparency and ambiguous methodology in the work "Expert Finding in the Legal Community Question Answering" [1, 2] pose significant challenges to the reproducibility of the proposed experiment. The outcome obtained after forcibly resolving these inherent problems is hardly comparable with the original results and arguably holds any value by itself.

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